

Effects of Team Cohesion on Selected Ethiopian Female Basketball Premier League Teams

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Abstract

This research aimed to study the effect of team cohesion on selected Ethiopian female basketball premier league teams and suggest possible alternatives that would create a cohesive team and improve the performance of athletes and the team. The sample of the subject consists of 2(100%) basketball coaches, 20(80%) Ethiopian sports academy women's basketball club players, and a total of twenty-two participants were included. Descriptive surveys and both quantitative and qualitative methods were employed to conduct this research. For this purpose, variable data suggests that the team cohesion of women players in their clubs has significantly impacted the quality of playing basketball in the Ethiopian sports academy women's basketball team. Questionnaires and observation were used to collect the data. The result of the study indicates that the team's members communicate smoothly, and both coaches use a democratic leadership style. Group size, communication breaks, and the coach's leadership style are factors affecting team cohesion. Finally, the major finding of this study is that team cohesion has a greater effect on individual and team performance.

Keywords: performance, team, effect, cohesion, and basketball

1.1 Introduction

Team Cohesion can be defined as the tendency for a group to be in unity while working towards a goal or to satisfy the emotional needs of its members (Albert V. Carron, 1982). This definition includes important aspects of cohesiveness, including its multidimensionality, dynamic nature, instrumental basis, and emotional dimension (Carron et al., 1989). Its multidimensionality refers to how cohesion is based on many factors. Its dynamic nature refers to how it gradually changes its strength and form over time from when a group is formed to when it is disbanded. Its instrumental basis refers to how people cohere for some purpose, whether for a task or social reasons. Its emotional dimension refers to how cohesion is pleasing to its group members. This definition can be generalized to most groups characterized by the abovementioned definition. These groups include sports teams, work groups, military units, fraternity groups, and social groups. However, it is important to note that other researchers claim that cohesion cannot be generalized across many groups.

Factors influencing team cohesion in sports teams include personal identity motives such as self-esteem, distinctiveness, meaning, and efficacy derived from team membership (Higgins & Herbert, 2013). Social identity motives, including feelings of belonging, meaning, and continuity associated with the team identity, also play a role in group identification (Thomas et al., 2017). Additionally, a shared belief in group distinctiveness contributes to collective identity and team cohesion (Caldeira et al., 2020). The coordination between players based on their perception of shared affordances and the emergence of collective behaviors are important for team synergies and cohesion (Sattari et al., 2022). Furthermore, novel field-based evidence on the associations between meaningful bonds of mutual reliance in a challenging team event and adolescent wellbeing (Cohen et al., 2023). Overall, understanding and addressing these various factors can enhance team cohesion in sports teams.

The effects of team cohesion on Ethiopian female basketball premier league teams can be understood through various dimensions of cohesion, including task and social cohesion, and their relationship with performance and psychological factors. Cohesion significantly influences team dynamics, impacting individual and collective outcomes. Dimensions of Team Cohesion include task cohesion, which refers to the degree to which team members work together to achieve common goals (Carron et al., 1985). High task cohesion is linked to improved performance and collective efficacy (Filho et al., 2014). Social Cohesion: Involves interpersonal relationships among team members. Strong social bonds can enhance communication and trust, which are crucial for team success (A. T. Haddera, 2015). Also, Psychological Impacts are Anxiety and Self-Confidence. Research indicates that female athletes often experience higher cognitive anxiety and

lower self-confidence compared to their male counterparts. This anxiety negatively correlates with perceptions of cohesion (A. T. Haddera, 2015). Enhanced cohesion can mitigate anxiety, fostering a supportive environment that boosts self-confidence (T. A. Haddera, n.d.). Coaching Influence is Leadership Styles: Coaches who adopt democratic and supportive leadership styles foster greater team cohesion, which in turn correlates with team success. Effective coaching strategies are essential for nurturing cohesion among female basketball teams (Getachew & Assefa, 2016). While the positive effects of cohesion are evident, excessive focus on cohesion might lead to conformity pressures, potentially stifling individual expression and creativity within the team. Balancing cohesion with individual autonomy is crucial for optimal team performance.

The Ethiopian Basketball Premier League represents the pinnacle of competitive basketball in the country (Tagesse, 2022). Understanding how team cohesion affects the performance of these elite clubs can provide valuable insights for coaches, players, and administrators aiming to optimize team dynamics and achieve sustained success (Eys et al., 2022). This study seeks to explore the team cohesion on Ethiopian female basketball premier league teams, shedding light on both the universal and context-specific factors that influence this dynamic.

This study can contribute a lot to female basketball team managers and coaches by increasing team cohesion. By the end, this study can find the major effects of team cohesion on female basketball teams so we can minimize factors that affect team cohesiveness. Different research has been conducted on this issue by different individuals and organizations. A qualitative study was conducted by (Eys et al. (2015)). According to this researcher, cohesion may drive performance for females, while performance may drive perceptions of cohesion for males. In essence, male and female teams differ in how cohesion is facilitated (e.g., faster development in male teams).

1.2 Statement of the problem

This study aims to show the effect of team cohesion on the selected Ethiopian female basketball premier league teams. To attain this, the researcher tried to see the research gap: not enough research has been conducted on the issue of team cohesion and female basketball in Ethiopia. In addition to the effects of team cohesion on the result of selected Ethiopian female basketball premier league teams, factors affecting team cohesion and how to develop team cohesion are variables to be studied.

The research questions are;

1. What are the factors that affect team cohesion?
2. Do the team members communicate smoothly?
3. Does effective team cohesion improve performance?
4. What kind of leadership style does the coach use?

1.3 Objectives of the study

. To identify the effect of team cohesion on the selected Ethiopian Female Basketball Premier League Teams

Specific objectives of the study are to:

1. To justify factors that affect team cohesion.
2. To identify the level of communication between players.
3. To check whether team cohesion improves the result or not.
4. To identify the leadership style of the coach.

1.4. Significance of the study

There are many beneficiaries of this study. The first beneficiaries are the Ethiopian sports academy and other premier league female basketball teams because this study proves the effect of team cohesion; the second beneficiaries are the Ethiopian female's national basketball team because the national team found cohesive players; finally, female basketballers will be more beneficiaries because cohesive players are the choice of current basketball coaches so that they can earn better. In addition to these beneficiaries, the basketball profession can use this study because team cohesion is a critical issue in modern basketball.

1.5. Delimitation of the study

Whatever the scope of this study is sport academy female basketball team, others also could benefit from the findings, but all people who follow this study should know that all the data in this study was gathered from the sport academy basketball players and coaches.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHOD

3.1. RESEARCH DESIGN

This part of the study deals with the research design, participants, instrumentation, procedures, and study analysis. A descriptive survey approach was used to carry out this research. A descriptive survey was used because it is particularly useful for describing the situation and understanding some information regarding the effect of team cohesion. Thus, a descriptive survey approach is best suited for this research. About the research methods indicated above, this research study followed a quantitative and qualitative research approach(Wang, 2022). The reason for this is that the researcher employed quantitative and qualitative approaches. In addition to the above reasons, the data obtained through structured questionnaires and observation can be quantified.

3.1. SUBJECT AND SAMPLING PROCEDURES

Participants in this study were women basketball players of the Ethiopian sports academy, and coaches participated in the study. Coach with a certification for coaching basketball and had completed the coaching course in basketball. All coaching participants had extensive coaching experience. Questions are asked regarding various coaching and athletic experiences, such as the training structure, years of experience coaching at these levels, and engagement in coaching development activities.

3.1.1 SOURCE OF DATA INSTRUMENTATION

This study followed both qualitative and quantitative research designs to obtain complete data. The following data collection instruments were used Training session observation with a checklist Questionnaire for 20 players and 2 coaching staffs. The researcher tries to see the previous documents on this issue to analyze the previous findings; the training session observation was done by using an observation checklist; semi-structured questionnaires were organized to obtain data from the respondents. Participants in this study were women basketball players of the Ethiopian sports academy and coaches of the same club. This sample team was selected based on the following criteria: Availability, Easy to transport; and - Proximity to the researcher 's working place. A non-probability method of sampling is used to determine respondents in this study. The convenience sampling (ease of access) technique is suited to the nature of the participant

QUESTIONNAIRE

A questionnaire is prepared and administered to the sample players to collect data regarding the team cohesion of women's basketball coaches and players. In order to elicit the necessary data, both questionnaires were constructed based on the review of related literature, consisting of two main sub-topics: I, personal profiles, and II, effects of team cohesion on the result of selected Ethiopian premier league female basketball teams. This was also constructed to follow the main themes of the research guiding questions. There are two sets of questions: some are close-ended, while most consist of open-ended questions, which, the researcher believes, would help the respondents write about their real feelings about the phenomena they are asked about. Even though analyzing the second set of questions is very difficult, the researcher believes it gives the respondents much freedom to suggest their subjective thoughts more appropriately than the first type of questions. Respondents were not asked to put their names on the questionnaires to satisfy the need for confidentiality. Instead, they were kindly requested to indicate their sex, age, qualifications, and experience regarding their background characteristics. English examined the questionnaires graduated student to avoid errors related to accuracy, fluency, and contents and to validate the frame items. My friend, who graduated from Addis Ababa University in the Department of English, also examined the questions to see if any corrections were needed and to determine whether they led to certain conclusions for the significant purpose of the study. Moreover, the instruments initially prepared were given to my advisor for comment on the extent to which the items were appropriate in securing the relevant information for the research. Based on the feedback obtained from my advisor, amendments were made. The researcher selected the questionnaire as a data-gathering tool because of its convenience for the investigation and suitability for survey research. Using the questionnaire makes the research less expensive and increases the likelihood of obtaining accurate information. However, by its nature, the questioner suffers from weaknesses such as a lack of opportunities to clarify issues and responses that cannot be supplemented with other information.

3.2.3 OBSERVATION

An observation was prepared to gather additional information. Five consecutive observations were carried out to accomplish the task. A well-organized checklist with nine important questions was created. Most of the questions are used to indicate whether there is team cohesion or not.

Besides, the questions were also examined by my friend Abdelaziz Hasan, who graduated from Addis Ababa University in the Department of Sport Science, to see if any corrections were needed and to determine

whether they led to certain conclusions for the significant purpose of the study. Moreover, the instruments initially prepared were given to my advisor to comment on the extent to which the items were appropriate in securing the relevant information for the research.

3.3 PROCEDURE

All participants were volunteered to participate in the study and were known to the primary researcher, who had worked with them and their teams. This already established relationship with the participants was perceived as beneficial and consistent with the researcher. A semi-structured interview, questionnaire and observation with check list were used in this study. This combined strategy offers the flexibility of probing and exploring certain subjects in greater depth. The standardized approach used in this study consisted of a series of pre-planned open-ended questions organized into a number of interrelated sections.

3.4.METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The content analysis of the data is based on the qualitative and quantitative research methods implemented to analyze the content of the data. Participants were allowed to clarify or change any of their responses. They were also asked whether they had any comments, questions, or concerns about the interviews. Second, an intercoder consistency check was used to ensure the researchers' data analysis was appropriate, minimizing researcher bias.

3.5 VALIDITY

Validity is the extent to which a test measures what it is supposed to measure. The question of validity is raised in the context of three points: the form of the test, the purpose of the test, and the population for whom it is intended. In the case of this study, the researcher decided to use concurrent validity to check whether it was valid or not. Concurrent validity is the degree to which the scores on a test are related to the scores on another, already established test administered at the same time or to some other valid criterion available at the same time. For example, a new simple test is to be used instead of an old cumbersome one, which is considered useful; measurements are obtained on both simultaneously.

3.6 RELIABILITY

Research requires dependable measurement. Measurements are reliable to the extent that they are repeatable and that any random influence that tends to make measurements different from occasion to occasion or circumstance to circumstance is a source of measurement error. Reliability is the degree to which a test consistently measures whatever it measures. Errors of measurement that affect reliability are random. To

check whether it is reliable or not, the researcher decided to use test-retest reliability, which is the degree to which scores are consistent over time. It indicates score variation from testing session to testing session due to measurement errors. The pilot study will be the best method to realize the reliability.

3.7 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study incorporates all the research components and follows the right procedure for the senior essay. The researcher also tries to check the reliability and validity of the research. On the other hand, ethical issues of research are also considered in this study. The researcher is also careful in sampling so as not to become biased.

4. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION PRESENTATION

In this section, the results obtained from the questionnaire and observation checklist are analyzed and interpreted using Percentages to analyze responses to close-ended items in the questionnaires and descriptive statements to interpret open-ended items in the questionnaires.

4.1. BACKGROUND CHARACTERISTICS OF THE STUDY GROUP

Based on the responses obtained from players and coaches, the characteristics of the study groups were examined in terms of their sex, age, and work experience. This section was present the analysis of the self-administered questionnaires and observation checklist. The respondents to the study include players and coaches.

Table1. Characteristics of respondents (players)

NO	ITEM		RESPONDANTS	
			FREQUENCY	PERCENTILE
1	Sex	Male	0	0
		Female	20	100
		Total	20	100
2	Age	Less than 20	8	40
		21-25	7	35
		26-30	5	25
		Total	20	100
3	Professional Experience	0-2	5	30
		3 -5	11	55
		6-10	8	15
		Total	20	100
4	Number of team or	1	5	25
		2	9	45
		3	5	30
		Total	20	100

As indicated, 100% of respondents are females because of the nature of the study. Regarding age, the majority, 40% of the players are less than 20; this indicates the team is young enough. 55% of the respondents also have enough professional experience, which also creates a conducive environment for team management. The last requested characteristic of the players was the number of teams they played for, and regarding this majority, 75% of the players played for more than 1 team. This also helps the players to share experiences with each other.

Table.2. Characteristics of Respondents (Coaches)

NO	ITEM		RESPONDENTS	
			FREQUENCY	PERCENTILE
1	Sex	Male	2	100
		Total	2	100
2	Age	Greater than 31	2	100
		Total	2	100
3	Professional Experience	3-5	2	50
		Greater than 10yrs	1	50
		Total	2	100
4	Educational level	Secondary educ.	2	100
		Total	2	100
5	Coaching License	A License	1	50
		B License	1	50
		Total	1	100

The table indicates that 100% of the coaching staff are males. It is known that the team is a women's club, so it is better to have women coaches regarding age 100% of the coaching staff is greater than 31, which is an age of better maturity compared with others. One of the coaches (the head coach), 50%, has professional experience of more than 10 years. This will be an important demand for the coaching staff. Regarding educational level, 100% of the coaching staff is in secondary education, which also hinders their work because football by itself is a science. Regarding the coaching license, 50% of the coaching staff has an A License, which is very important for the current view of modern basketball

4.2 DATA OBTAINED FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Table.3. Response from the questionnaire (Players)

NO.	ITEM	N	MEAN	SD	YES		NO	
					F	%	F	%
1	Are you satisfied with playing in this team?	20	1.20	0.410	16	80	4	20
2	Do you like the style of play of this team?	20	1.35	0.489	13	65	7	35
3	Some of my best friends are on this team	20	1.25	0.444	15	75	5	25
4	We all take responsibility for any poor performance by our team?	20	1.45	0.510	11	55	9	45
5	Are members of your team play down than a team?	20	1.70	0.470	6	30	14	70
6	Do you have smooth communication your team mate?	20	1.05	0.224	19	95	1	5
7	Does effective team cohesion can performance?	20	1.0	0.000	20	100	0	0
8	Does the coach treat all players equal	20	1.30	0.470	14	70	6	30
9	Does incentive money lead to better cohesion?	20	1.00	0.000	20	100	0	0

N= Total number of respondents, F= Frequency, SD= Standard Deviation

As indicated in the above table, 80% of the respondents are satisfied with their team. This is also a good indicator of team cohesion in that club. A player's satisfaction with their team is one characteristic of a cohesive team. Regarding the second question, 65% of the team members like the style of play in their team; players of cohesive teams devote themselves to the style of play in their team, even if it is not interesting. The third question is about the number of best friends they have on their team; according to the calculated data, 35% of the team members said that some of their best friends are on this team, meaning that the majority of the team members are the best friend to each other this also is one characteristic of a cohesive team. On the fourth question, 55% of the respondents said they all take responsibility for any loss or poor performance by their team. This shows that the team is cohesive because most of them share the team's responsibilities cooperatively. Only 30% of the respondents confirmed that team members play independently rather than as a team. This indicates that the majority of the team members play as a team. For that matter, the team is said to be cohesive.

Regarding question number six, 95% of the respondents said that they have smooth communication with their teammates; as we know, communication is the prerequisite for building team cohesion, so we can conclude that players in this team have great communication with each other. Almost 100% of the respondents on the seventh question confirmed that effective team cohesion can improve performance; this means that team cohesion and performance are directly proportional. About question eight, 70% of the respondents said that the coach treats all players equally; if players are treated equally, the team would have a better spirit. This also is important to build a cohesive team. On the last close-ended question, 100% of the respondents confirmed that incentive money leads to better team cohesion. This pocket money is given to players during every win so that players become cohesive to win and get that money. Here are frequently appearing answers for the open-ended question. Twenty respondents were asked about factors affecting team cohesion. The frequently appearing answers are a lack of effective communication between players, a coach's leadership quality, and personal interest, which can hinder the development of team cohesion.

Table 4. Response from the questionnaire (Coaches)

NO.	ITEM	N	MEAN	SD	YES		NO	
					F	%	F	%
1	Did you take a course on sports psychology?	2	2.00	0.000	0	0	2	100
2	Do you treat all players equally?	2	1.00	0.000	2	100	0	0
3	Do you think that you have a cohesive team?	2	1.00	0.00	2	100	0	0
4	Does effective team cohesion leads to better performance?	2	1.00	0.000	2	100	0	0
5	Do your players have smooth communication with you?	2	1.00	0.000	2	100	0	0
6	Does incentive money lead to better team cohesion?	2	1.50	0.707	1	50	1	50

N= Total number of respondents, SD= Standard Deviation, F= Frequency

As indicated in the table above, 100% of the respondents did not take a course on sports psychology. As we know, team cohesion is one component of sports psychology. Every coach needs to have scientific knowledge of football, and psychological preparation is also one of its components.

Regarding the second question, 100% of the respondents said that they treat all players equally. If the coaches treat all players in the team equally, there will be smooth communication with all players, as communication is a key concept in team cohesion. In the third question, 100% of the respondents agreed that they have a cohesive team; accordingly, cohesive teams have better performance. The respondents are confident in the cohesiveness of their team. 100% of the respondents on question number four said that effective team cohesion leads to better team cohesion, which indicates that effective team cohesion and performance are directly proportional. Regarding the level of coach communication with all players, 100% of the respondents smoothly communicated with the players. This smooth communication is important to build team cohesion.

The last close-ended question is about the use of incentive money; 50% of the respondents confirmed that incentive money leads to better team cohesion, but the second respondent needed a precondition in relation to giving incentive money. The two coaches have three open-ended questions, and the data is interpreted as follows. The first question, listing important points that help us build cohesive team communication and treatment, has frequent answers from both respondents. This indicates that smooth communication and equal treatment of players are crucial for team cohesion. Regarding the second open-ended question, which is about factors affecting team cohesion, group size, communication breakdown, and the coach's leadership style, there are frequent answers from both respondents. If you have a large team size, it is difficult to manage the players, and this also can affect your team cohesiveness. At the same time, if you have players of different ages, their communication can be broken down, which also affects team cohesion. The third open-ended question is about the style of leadership they prefer; both respondents confirmed that they prefer to use a democratic leadership style.

4.3 DATA OBTAINED FROM OBSERVATION

This data was gathered from the observation during five consecutive training and game observations. Members of the team liked and cared about each other. This shows that the team is cohesive. The coach is a democrat while leading his team. As the coaches prefer the democratic leadership style, they have applied it during training sessions, which helps them communicate smoothly with their players. The members communicate smoothly with each other. The important issue in team cohesion is communication, and there is no communication breakdown in the team. This is one behavior of a cohesive team. The members never depended upon the group leader for direction. Every player assumes they should share responsibilities regarding their team, which is also important to keep team cohesiveness. There was friction and anger between the members. But it is not such a conflict. Rather, it is the nature of the football game, and the coach manages it quickly. The members were not distant and withdrawn from each other. The researcher observed that the players are close enough to each other and never withdraw from each other; this indicates the level of cohesiveness of one team. The members communicate smoothly with their coaches. There is no communication breakdown between players and coaches because the coaches treat all players equally. There are no members who reject and distrust each other; rather, they share ideas and experiences during training. This also has a positive impact on team cohesion and performance. The team players perform well in the game. During my game observation, the team looked cooperative, supported each other, and played as a team. Most players perform well in the game, which is the effect of team cohesion.

5.1. CONCLUSION

After an intensive discussion of the findings on the effect of team cohesion on selected Ethiopian Premier League female basketball teams, the researcher concludes that the teams' members communicate smoothly (95%). There is effective communication between the players and the coaches, too. Both coaches use a democratic leadership style. Democratic leadership style is the most preferred style of leadership. Both coaches also confirmed that the democratic leadership style is their best. The team members, including the coaches, believed that team cohesion leads to better performance (100%), so better performance is the effect of team cohesion. The researcher also confirmed this during his consecutive observations. Group size, communication breaks, and the coach's leadership style affect team cohesion. The two coaches also confirmed this.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations are significant for the Ethiopian sports academy female basketball team and other team players and coaches to create a conducive environment and improve their performance.

- Communication is a prerequisite for team cohesion, and female basketball team coaches should work to create smooth communication between players and coaches. Smooth communication is the aim for effective team cohesion.
- Some factors contribute greatly to building team cohesion; one of them is incentive money. Incentive money increases players' motivation, which also leads to better team cohesion. So, Ethiopian Premier League basketball teams should use this method to increase team cohesion.
- Team cohesion has a positive effect on individual performance and team performance, so coaches should follow up on their team's cohesiveness level by using a group cohesion questionnaire. This helps them know their team cohesion level, as it improves performance.
- Treating players well and communicating are ways to build a cohesive team. Coaches should apply these methods in their daily training program and in-game situations, and as a result, teams become cohesive.
- All the coaching staff should follow the same leadership style, which should be democratic. Every rule and regulation should be interpreted equally for all players.

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